

Phenanthrene from 9-Hydroxyphenanthrene (A Note).

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9-Hydroxyphenanthrene (5 g.) (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 418, 591) was heated in a flask in a metal-bath with selenium (5 g.) at 300-310° for 10 hours. The temperature was then raised to 330° in course of 6 hours and it was further heated at that temperature for 8 hours. The product was dissolved in alcohol and a saturated solution of picric acid added when a picrate (0.3 g.) was precipitated. It was filtered, washed and twice recrystallised from alcohol, m.p. 145°.

Phenanthrene, regenerated from pure picrate, melts at 100°. The identities of phenanthrene and its picrate were confirmed by mixed m.p. with authentic specimens.

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